

SPORTS' EFFECT ON SOCIALIZING OF CONVICTS AND PRISONERS: EXAMPLE OF ANTALYA PROVINCE, TURKEY

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Abstract:

In this research, it has been tried to determine the position of sports or sports activities as a tool to increase or decrease harmony and union in social relations. The expected outcome of as assumption of our research is sports to increase social union or to provide positive contribution to build harmonious human relations. Antalya province L type Prison, which hosts 1450 convicts, chosen as the research area. The function of sport, as a social union tool, is one of the aims of this study. For this aim, one-on-one interviews are made with the prisoners and convicts. In second phase, volunteers were selected to play sports and for 10 weeks soccer, which is a team sport and attracted the greatest interest of convicts, was played. This study was conducted with 50 convicts who play sports and 50 convicts who do not play sports. The findings, which obtained as result, were seen low specific to certain indicators and were seen rather strong in some. Sports activities increase harmony and social union in human relations. The validity of this judgement is confirmed in the relations of people with themselves in small group relations, in relation with the surrounding social world, and finally in relation to public administration units.

Keywords: prison, sports, convict, socializing

1. Introduction

The main aim of this study is to determine the position of sports as a tool to increase or decrease harmony and union in social relations of convicts in prison. The adopted assumption or expected outcome of this research is sports to increase social union or to provide positive contribution to build harmonious human relations. In order to

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determine whether this expectation has been realized, Antalya province L Type prison chosen as the research area. The main reason of choosing a prison as research area is because it is an accepted fact that the people who live in prison are deviated from social order identifiers.

As an integral part of the basic education of sport and its functions, foresees the undertaking of new assignments in accordance with the changing conditions of the sport as an obligatory result of industrialization, mechanization, urbanization etc. coming to the contemporary society... Today, people are increasingly pushed into loneliness and abstraction and buckle under to their environment and need to express themselves and creativity (Fişek, 1985).

This study has been deemed necessary for the purpose to document and determinate that sports can be functional as a tool which increases social unity between the people who are detached from social identifiers. It makes it possible to say that it can be functional more easily within the social structure (Erkal, 1986).

Is there any difference in socializing effects between convicts and prisoners who do and do not participate sportive activities? First reason that makes this research important is to study sports as a social unity tool, at least in Turkey, it is not yet sufficiently studied. If sportive activities increase social unity, the cost of solving problems due to social disorganization or conflict related ones will be reduced. In this context, increasing the harmony of the people with the dominant norms of the society and those who seem to be deviated, in part, by the synonymously interpretable law, will also cause the problems of the administration to be avoided from the very beginning or to become more easily manageable. The main aim of this study is to determine the position of sports as a tool to increase or decrease harmony and union in social relations of convicts in prison.

It can be said that humans are social living creatures or 'homo socius' from the moment that humanity's emergence. People have felt the necessity of gathering, helping each other or organized as hierarchical units for both surviving against wild nature and to live better. Society is the name of both these necessities and organization that this wishes created (Giddens, 1992).

As in the other small scale social units such as prisons, family, circle of friends, circle of neighbors, it can be seen as surrounding social structure's reflection or examples (Turgut, 1986). Goffman, who has a special interest in this particular subject, with the basis of his own sense of sociological theory, names prisons different than open social institutions as "closed social institutions". Prisons are the places where freedom is restricted and people who are entered in are detached from other social identifiers such as occupation, income, education. In prison, the rules of conduct are given. Convicts and prisoners have to obey these rules. This disengagement refers some kind of depersonalization. However, creation of personality and its presentation activity are re-executed within this new environment's conditions. It can be sorted as formal rules, which regulates daily living, being present in inspections in day and night, participating to culture classes and courses which are arranged by management, cleaning, food distribution, making the renovation duties that given, obey certain time

limit in visiting days, do not keep inconvenient substances in wards, using the convenient writing style in written letters, obey the personnel and obey waking time and time for bed, obey the rules of be in the sick list etc. (Goffman,1959).

Apart from these, there are rules that they have to obey because of the conditions which are not formal. These rules are providing convicts live in harmony with each other in the narrow area where they live. Ward rules which are determined by ward keepers and accepted by convicts, are the natural rules, which are originated from ward environment, such as television watching hours, making salads, ward cleaning, provisions which are came in canteen days and using other materials for ward. The convicts who do not obey these rules are alienated and left alone (Goffman, 1959).

Parsons states that social system consists of institutionalized values. Sports carry the characteristics of being unifying part of social system and consists institutionalized values which are stipulated in terms of social system. According to Parsons in order to examine personality system, it is necessary to explain motivation, drive and necessity concepts. Motivation is the energy that produced organically and allows behavior to be performed in action. Drive is the physiological energy that makes the action possible and an innate tendency. Parsons determined that personality system can be examined similar to social system. Accordingly, sports can be discussed and evaluated as unifying tool of system in terms of both individually and socially. Both the personality system and social system must be discussed with the aspects of institutionalized and internalized by individual. In consideration of sports as a harmony tool, relation between individual, society and culture must be discussed together. The evaluation of personality system related to social and cultural system is executed with socialization process. Socialization, basically, becomes apparent with three main aspects: 1.Achieving culture, 2.Integration of culture with personality, 3.Harmony to social environment (Gür, 1983).

Socialization is defined as the process of obtaining information, models, values and symbols, in short, thinking and hearing forms' peculiar to society/community that one is lived in.

Sports are an active agent in providing the harmony between division of labor, which is increased with social differentiation that is the most common feature of the modern societies, and social unity (Swingewood, 1986). Sport is one of the most important factors in the social structure of society managing of uneasiness, reducing deviant behaviors and harmonization of them with norms, directing tension to society's interest, as well as the models of conformity and conflict. Sports, as organized sportive activities set, sometimes have the characteristics of a phenomenon and sometimes have the characteristics of an event with its occurrence features in society (Karaküçük, 1995).

It is a phenomenon that is deeply involved in social life of today's people and shapes according to the social structure. Sports, finance expenses, the number of participants and viewers, movies, books, caricatures related to sports, the time that spent, sport equipment can be documented as sports' documents. (Gür, 1983). Sports delivers solution to this danger which is in front of modern people with creating dynamic and stress, which is caused by daily life, free environment and it helps

preventive medicine with its form of bringing healthy life. Alongside this function of sports, it is obvious that it has positive effects on development of social and individual character. For this reason, developed countries give sports high importance and starting from early ages there is sports and gym programs applied to children (Snyder, 1990).

Sports, which is one of the most important activity field of our age and in the condition as "a developed industry", is facing with a dangerous situation in other frame also alongside the manipulations of social, economic, cultural and political (Şahin, 2018).

The competitions, which include the feelings of winning, losing, ambition, superiority and performed as individual or team sport but carries a competitive spirit and have certain rules, have different meaning for the viewers and performers. In the competition sports which performed individually, the branch he/she performed becomes a profession. Team sports can be performed, in modern institutions and organizations, for the purpose of increasing the personnel's relations and increase work efficiency. There is no field that sports has been or used in and has felt its presence. From family to school, from school to workplace, holdings and politics. This kind of great power can be used in the society's any part for any purpose.

As it is known, sports are an important activity field with its contribution of individual and social health and moral aspects (Şahin, 2018). Sports create a strict bond between its past and society's past. This strong interest is because of sports forms through social processes. For this reason, sports do not occur autonomously, especially, it occurs through relations in society and it changes and regenerates (Gür, 1983).

2. Materials and Methods

This research was carried out in Antalya L Type Prison. In prison, there are convicts and prisoners who are in different groups of crime. As of the date of this research is conducted, the total number of the prisoners and convicts in prison is 1450. The research sample is chosen a total of 100 people, 50 of them play sports and 50 of them are not. Convicts are living in wards which are two-tier and total of 140 m². For each ward, there are open areas which are called airing and they are 50 m². There are a total of 61 wards in prison. The convicts', who are living in wards, number are changing in between 15 and 30.

Field research is carried out in the term of 2015 spring (March, April, May). It can be said that the research is carried out in two stages. In the first stage of the research, a soccer playing group was created with 50 of the volunteer convicts.

In the second stage of the research, two wards were chosen where their convicts are both have the similar demographic characteristics and never played sports before but willing to play. In this stage, secondly, a limited number of convicts were chosen to create and play a soccer team from the people in the wards who are volunteer to do so. These convicts were regularly trained and practiced sports for 10 weeks. In practice three days of week has been chosen and sports practices have been performed 2 hours a day. However, when convicts are wanted, this practice hour is exceeded. For the first 6

weeks, convicts are practiced regularly and given basic information. And in the last 4 weeks, matches were played in between both the teams in ward and other ward's teams.

The interviews, based on the questionnaire, which was conducted with the field research, prison personnel and ward clerk and aimed to find out if there were any changes related to the sports in the conduct of convicts, was conducted after 10 weeks of sports practice. It can be said that the research, which is on the effects of sports on the questionnaire that asked to convicts, is a descriptive field research. For this reason, the obtained basic findings are given in simple frequency distribution tables.

3. Findings

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Birth Places

Group	Birth Place	f	%
Control Group	City center	25	50
	District	19	38
	Town	2	4
	Village	4	8
	Total	50	100,0
Experiment Group	City center	28	56
	District	10	20
	Town	5	10
	Village	7	14
	Total	50	100,0

It is determined that the participants in control group 51,1% of them are born in city center, 38,3% of them are born in district, 6,4% of them are born in village, 4,3% of them are born in town and in experiment group, 61,0% of them are born in city center, 19,5% of them are born in district, 12,2% of them are born in village and 7,3% of them are born in town.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Educational Status

Group	Educational status	f	%
Control Group	Illiterate	1	2
	Literate	3	6
	Primary School	3	6
	Secondary School	16	32
	High School	16	35
	University 2 years	7	14
	University 4 years	4	8
	Total	50	100,0
Experiment Group	Literate	2	4
	Primary School	8	16
	Secondary School	8	16
	High School	26	52
	University 2 years	5	10
	Total	50	100,0

It is determined that the research's participants' educational status in control group the highest value is 31,9% as secondary school and high school and the lowest value is 2,1% as illiterate and in experiment group the highest value is 56,1% as high school and the lowest value 4,9% as literate.

Table 3: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Marital Status

Group	Marital status	f	%
Control Group	Married	17	34
	Single	23	46
	Divorced	10	20
	Total	50	100,0
Experiment Group	Married	22	44
	Single	25	50
	Divorced	3	6
	Total	50	100,0

It is determined that the research's participants' marital status in control group the highest value 47,9% of them are single, 35,4% of them are married 16,7% of them are divorced and in experiment group 51,2% of them are single, 43,9% of them are married and 4,9% of them are divorced.

Table 4: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Families' Approximate Monthly Income

Group	Monthly Income	f	%
Control Group	0-100 TL	17	34
	101-150 TL	6	12
	151-200 TL	11	22
	More	16	32
	Total	50	100,0
Experiment Group	0-100 TL	8	16
	101-150 TL	4	8
	151-200 TL	2	4
	More	36	72
	Total	50	100,0

It is determined that the research's participants' families' monthly income in control group the highest value is 35% as 0-100TL, the lowest value is 10% as 101-150 TL and in the experiment group, the highest value is 72,2% as more than 200 TL, the lowest value is 2,8% 151-200 TL.

Table 5: Comparison of the answers of the question “do you think that activities related to recreation in prison is enough” between Experiment Group and Control Group

Answers	Frequency and % value	Control Group	Experiment group last test	Total
Yes	f	9	1	10
	%	90,0	10,0	100,0
No	f	41	48	89
	%	46,06	53,93	100,0
Other	f	0	1	1
	%	0	100,0	100,0
Total	f	50	50	100
	%	54,5	45,5	100,0

It is determined that there is significant difference between answers of the question “do you think that activities related to recreation in prison is enough” between experiment group and control group ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6: Comparison of the answers of the question “who would you like to give free time activities to you by” between Experiment Group and Control Group

Answers	Frequency and % value	Control Group	Experiment group last test	Total
By prison officers	f	1	14	15
	%	6,7	93,3	100,0
One of our people	f	1	4	5
	%	20,0	80,0	100,0
An expert from outside	f	43	23	66
	%	65,2	34,8	100,0
Other	f	45	41	86
	%	52,3	47,7	100,0
Total	f	50	50	100
	%	6,7	93,3	100,0

It is determined that there is significant difference between answers of the question “who would you like to give free time activities to you by” between experiment group and control group ($p < 0.05$). According to this, it is determined that the individuals in the control group are more likely to agree that these activities should be given by an outside person compared to the individuals in the experiment group, while the individuals in the experiment group are more likely to agree that the prison officers should give these activities.

Table 7: Comparison of the answers of the question “if there is free time activities, which ones are you participating” between Experiment Group and Control Group

Answers	Frequency and % value	Experiment pre-test	Experiment last test	Total
Manipulative skills	f	18	7	25
	%	78,9	21,1	100,0
Painting works	f	0	4	4
	%	,0	100,0	100,0
Musical works	f	6	5	11
	%	60,0	40,0	100,0

Sportive works	f	14	22	36
	%	38,7	61,3	100,0
Cultural works	f	5	9	14
	%	25,0	75,0	100,0
Other	f	7	3	10
	%	75,0	25,0	100,0
Total	f	50	50	100
	%	51,5	48,5	100,0

It is determined that there is significant difference between answers of the question “if there is free time activities, which ones are you participating” between experiment group and control group ($p < 0.05$). According to this, it was determined that the individuals in experiment group are usually participate in manipulative skills, and in their free times participate in sportive works.

4. Results and Recommendations

As a result of our research, we can say that, compared to convicts and prisoners who regularly conduct sports and convicts and prisoners who do not play sports, there is a lasting effect on the socialization of convicts and prisoners. This effect is influential on many issues such as making friends, group participation, feel valued, become tolerant, sense of competition, teamwork. The obtained result can be interpreted as sports' positive effect on all society members is valid on convicts and prisoners also. In this frame, it is a fact that sports can be more effectively adapted to the lives of convicts and prisoners and their compatibility with society can be improved.

We can suggest following suggestions based on the findings we have obtained as a result of our research:

1. It is seen that the level of education of convicts and prisoners are low. At the same time, there should be a support on their educational processes. Ministry of Justice and Ministry of Education should take precautions on this subject.
2. Convicts and prisoners should be able to continue to conduct their education and training services and activities in the Prisons more systematically and more regularly, and guidance on prison sports activities should be provided for them.
3. In order to increase the sporting opportunities of convicted and prisoners, Ministry of Justice General Directorate of Prisons and Detention Houses should create special sports areas for convicts and improve the physical conditions by increasing the training opportunities in this area.
4. To provide that convicts and prisoners participate in all kinds of sportive activities, prison management, sports clubs and local governments need to be efficient and active.
5. The possibility of playing sports should be provided in prisons, especially team sports should be supported. This will facilitate the life of the convicts as more compatible people in prisons and thus improve the security of the prison to the

point of dynamic security as well as make the prison management's rehabilitation works easier.

6. Sports activities to be carried out in prisons will positively affect the convicts' rehabilitation activities in terms of both physical and mental health and will shorten adjustment processes to the society after their release.
7. Sporting facilities in prisons should be provided at the professional level through the staff of physical education teachers. The domain and nature of a sporting activity carried out in this way will be better defined.
8. There are scarcely any study about the socialization of convicts and prisoners in our country. Researchers should be inclined and contribute to this area.

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